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Partition and the North West Frontier of India: The Case Study of North-West Frontier Province

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Abstract

The paper would attempt to highlight the internal political ambience of the NWFP on the eve of partition. It would delve in to the British strategic concerns which shaped and orchestrated political actions of the British Governors at the Provincial level. Moreover, the paper would be a refreshing reassessment of men and events which shaped the partition. The study of responses of the Political Parties, the idiosyncrasies of the native tribes, manoeuvrings of the religious leaders of the region would be the master key to understand the separation of the North Western Frontier Province.

Keywords British Strategic Concerns, Political Ambience of NWFP, Religious Leaders, Tribals.

Introduction

The decisive platform for the separation of North Western Frontier Province from the Indian dominion were created by the events during the last decade before the partition. The Frontier Congress was voted to power in the provincial election held in 1946. What happened during the last two years which turned the table and North Western Frontier Province opted for Pakistan would be examined in the paper.

Objective of study

The objective of the study is to understand the entire process keeping in mind the topography, strategic location, the cultural religious essence and above all the British strategic concerns. Furthermore, the frontier Governors manoeuvres distinctively shaped the politics of the region.

Review of Literature

The North western Frontier Province earlier known as gateway to India and its strategic importance was immense. On its west lies an international border with Afghanistan, in the east it nestled with the Gilgit agency in Kashmir and Punjab; to the south with Baluchistan.[1]

The province embraces three distinct geographical regions – district of Hajara, the settled trans – Indus districts of Peshawar, Kohat, Bannu, Mardan and D I Khan. A rugged mountain region between them is a vast tribal belt and the border of Afghanistan. The tribal belt for administrative purposes, was divided in to five political agencies. – Malakand, Kurram Khyber, North and South Waziristan. Kabul is just 50 miles from the borders of Khurram Agency in the NWFP. The important tribes of the tribal belt were the Afridis around the Khyber, Mehsuds between Tochi and Gomal rivers and swat; Wazirs between rivers Khurram and Gomal, Mohmands and lesser-known others[2].

As for the settled districts of Hazara, Punjabi Muslim dominated and D I Khan Jats were predominantly non- pathans. In 1849 the settled districts of the region were taken over by British from the Sikhs and the frontier line was laid down in 1893 between NWFP and Afghanistan thereby separating Pashtun and Baloch ethnic groups of both sides but Durand line was proved to be a porous frontier as tribes as a whole refused to sever their ties with their kinsmen across the Durand line. Under British rule NWFP was the most vulnerable area.[3]

As way back in 1808, the fear of Napoleon onslaughts through Persia and Afghanistan, was the principal preoccupation and security concern for the Britishers. In 19th century Russian advance in Central Asia after her forward movement blocked in Europe with its defeat in Crimean war 1854-56, focused on expansion in Asia. The British strategy was to use North West region as base to contain Russian ambition. These concerns intensified after Russian incorporation of central Asian region of Kokand, Khiva Bukhara including the cities of Tashkent and Samarkand in 1860s and 1870s which brought Russian frontier within few hundred miles away from India. Hence North Western Frontier of India for the British was the most sensitive of all the frontiers of the Empire.[4]

British built railway network to Khyber and Bolan passes, constructed road from Gilgit in Hunza, posted agents to monitor Russian activities to keep the areas of western approaches free from Russian influence. Hence, in the corridors of power there were unending debate among the authorities of how to control the frontier.

NWFP came in to being in 1901. Curzon With a view to bring the frontier under closer imperial control, devised a new scheme to place the province directly under the Government of India. For security reasons all the key officials, political agents and Deputy Commissioners were drawn from the coveted Indian political service.[5]

Further, the Government of India Act 1935 raised the NWFP at the level of other Provinces. The residents of urban areas were predominantly Hindus and Sikhs who were around 10 percent of the population. More than 90 percent of the population were Muslims residing in the rural areas. The British provincial Governor held the direct charge of the tribal areas, insulated it from the spheres of the external influences. The act further did not extend the authority of the elected ministers deliberately on issues related with the Tribals.[6]

Though the religious divide was over-shadowed by ethnicity –among Pakhtun, or loosely referred to as pathans who were in majority. Further, extension of land alienation act of 1904 to the frontier meant creation of landlord class. Landlords among them were influential khans representing the tribe, and honorary titles as khan sahib, khan bahadur and nawab were conferred by the British.

Political activity in the Frontier Province became prominent with the rise of Khan Abdul gaffar khan, who in 1929 formed an organization called Afghan Jirga to reform Pakhtun society, called khudai khitmatgar whose basic tenets identified as Pakhtun nationalism; had moral and less sectarian and political appeal. Their movement was known as Red Shirts. During the Civil Disobedience movement both Afghan jirga and khudai khitmatgars were formally affiliated to the Congress.[7]

Ideologically Gaffar khan was quite close to Gandhi, got sobriquet of Frontier Gandhi for his unflinching faith in non-violence as political creed and he never aspired for political office and was active participant in the national independence movement against the British. In contrast his elder brother was highly anglicized, held degree in medicine from England, married to English wife. Unlike his younger brother he was ideologically a constitutionalist, led the party and held ministerial office.[8]

The identity in the region was infused with religion and ethnicity. Mullas and maulvis mobilised the tribals. Fakir of Ipi and others played similar role in numerous incidents of tribal uprising against the British in Malakand for almost two decades 1893-1918 and in north Waziristan in 1930s and later half of 1940s exhausted and consumed the resources. However, a serious drawback under the government of India Act 1935, was that the area directly administered by the Government of India. Hence even the ministry of Frontier Congress formed under the Premier Dr. Khan Shahib in 1937 had no authority to control the situation and to punish the erring officials to solve the situation of tribal raids.[9]

However, George Cuningham who joined the Province as Governor in March 1937 build an excellent rapport with the premier khan sahib. His acquaintances with the region started earlier when he was appointed as private secretary of Lord Irwin from 1926-to 1930. Further, he was placed at Peshawar as member of provincial executive council for another 5 years (1932-36) and acquired first-hand knowledge of the Police, Finance Judiciary and Revenue Administration of the Province. What endeared him was his competence in Urdu diction spoken with remarkable purity of language and style.[10]

Despite Congress disciplinary injunctions, Khan Sahib attended official Parties, dressed in casuals rather usual khaddar and Gandhi cap. Khan sahib and his family's (lady Cuningham and Mrs Mary Khan) growing closeness and intimacy with the Governor

house popped up a lot of adverse comments in the regional press and wreaked their anti - Imperialist stance which discredited the Party.[11]

Further, while in office Cunningham in July 1938 handled the tribal raids in settled districts and in the border district of Bannu and D I Khan very smoothly. Moreover, the tumultuous events of the National Movement were also handled with maturity and coolness. Despite strict instructions by Viceroy to arrest Congress leaders during the announcement of Individual Satyagraha, and Quit India Movement, he lightly took the political threats and his response was normal as compared to other provincial administrators[12].

On the eve of the 2nd world War in 1939 along with other provinces the Frontier ministry also resigned on the directives of the Congress where Congress opted for non-cooperation with the British war effort. Khan also followed the suit. Cunningham's low key and non- confrontationalist approach towards Anti-Imperialist events and calmness in dealing with Delhi and with provincial leaders was appreciated widely. During the critical phase of war in 1943-44, his personal effort in managing Wazir and Mashud tribes displayed an innate skill and wisdom. There, the religious leader Fakir of Ipi was a major source of trouble who was generously funded and resourced by the Japanese and German agents as war progressed and campaign of Burma threatened the security of British Raj in the east.[13]

Against this backdrop warm and intimate relations developed between Cunningham and Khan sahib who formed the government again in February in 1945. The formation of Second Congress Ministry was a landmark.

However, the continuation of the ministry after Cunningham's superannuation in march 1946 after serving in frontier for nine years was threatened with the new incumbent Governor- Olaf Caroe. Earlier harmonious relationship and cordiality was entirely disrupted.

Before the appointment as Governor of NWFP, Olaf Caroe had been foreign secretary in Delhi from 1939 to 1946, and worked as a Principal advisor to two Viceroy's -Linlithgow and Wavell on British India's policy to forestall Soviet expansion in Afghanistan, Sinkiang and in the region of the Persian Gulf.[14]

Additionally, Olaf was trying to use American presence in Peshawar and also tried to educate the State Department on the usefulness from the Western point of view of the creation of Pakistan. His book on the theme later collated and published as Wells of Power which emphasised that North Western region was vital from where the British had restrained Russia. V.P. Menon, the distinguished civil servant and advisor on constitutional reform to three viceroys- Linlithgow, Wavell and Mountbatten in his book the Transfer of Power in India had endorsed these arguments.[15]

Further After the culmination of the second world war, an appraisal of the long-term policy required to safeguard the strategic interests of the British empire encapsulated in the secret report that Britain must retain its military connection with the subcontinent irrespective of political constitutional changes there and in this context special importance of North West of India was stressed. The report also proposed detachment of Baluchistan from India as its coast lies to the north of Gulf of Oman that leads to Persian Gulf. Churchill, Amry, the secretary of state and Lord Wavell, Viceroy (1943- 47) were among the British strategists who grasped the interrelated factors that after the British withdrawal, the Indian National Congress Leaders would form the Government in India, would work out their own foreign policy and defence priorities, unhampered by British concerns. Wavell was convinced that leaders of the Congress Party would not cooperate with Britain on defence matters as rulers of independent India.[16]

Thus, to safeguard British strategic interest, the idea of partitioning of India had started to circulate in British political- military circles. Hence to forge an alliance with the Muslim league party, Viceroy Linlithgow took the initiative to build up Jinnah as sole spokesman of the Muslims of India and, his successor Wavell planned a blue print, keeping it secret to avoid any impression of British hand in the division of India. [17]

Wavell as early as in February 1946, produced a blue print detailing the areas of British India that should go to Pakistan and the British authorities were enthusiastic proponents of Pakistan which would cooperate with British in military matters. Henceforth, with the tacit support of British officials, Muslim league in NWFP boosted its propaganda for Pakistan. Jinnah tapped people other than Pathans or politicians to reinforce his position in the tribal belt.[18]

In this context examining the activities of Iskender Mirza, a Bengali Muslim, an outstanding officer of Indian political service is quite necessary to understand the gradual growth of Muslim League in the region. Iskender Mirza spent most of his services in North Western province managing relations with the tribes of the frontier. Jinnah first met him in 1943 while he was serving as joint secretary in the ministry of defence in New Delhi and asked Iskender Mirza to resign from the Government of India and return to the tribal territories thereby urging him to take extraordinary steps to mobilise tribals in favour of league for preserving the interest of Muslims of India. Iskender Mirza's expertise with tribal affairs came in handy for Pakistan when as the defence secretary in new state he helped to organise tribal Lashkar militia which invaded Kashmir few months later. [19]

There was clear impression that official machinery was geared up for the League at the behest of British authorities when Jinnah visited the province in November 1945 and was a big boost to the League's campaign. Further, Jinnah's call for Muslim vote was forcefully echoed by pir of Manaki who evoked the Shariat to cast vote in favour of league. However, Pakhtun ethnic loyalties proved stronger than communal consciousness for Islam which formed subordinate part of their identity and turned out - a grave handicap for the league.[20]

The propaganda of establishment of domination of Hindu Raj and religious cry was unreal for average Pathan villagers and did not appeal. The election result showed pakhtun preference for the Congress. The party garnered 51 percent votes in Pakhtun constituency and 57.9 percent in other constituencies while Muslim league percentage was 39.40 and 37.45 respectively. However, League emerged as representative in non - Pakhtun Muslim area.[21]

The Frontier Congress Ministry under premiership of Khan Sahib sworn in on 9th march 1946 for the third time. However, the demand for Pakistan grew even more intense and later within months Pathans rejecting Pakistan as claimed by the Congress previously, turned out not to be valid.

Olaf Caroe, the Governor of the Province emerged as principal actor for his role in the chain of developments that led to transfer of power in the NWFP. The period between October 1946 and Caroe's unceremonial exit in June 1947 witnessed a remarkable transformation in the political scenario in Peshawar as events outside the frontier also begun to have a direct powerful bearing on the political developments.[22]

Nehru on 2nd sept 1946 assumed charge in the governor general executive council and given the portfolio of external affairs department which included tribal affairs and tribal areas. Caroe recorded in clear terms his objections to viceroy Wavell that tribal affairs should not be handed over non- Muslim member of the Viceroy's council. After Nehru took over the new charge, trouble arose in the tribal areas and to control it arial action mounted against the tribes. The League misrepresented the reality on the ground and the bombing of the tribal areas was in popular imagination made Nehru's new regime responsible for it. [23]

After the Rejection of cabinet mission on 16th August Jinnah's direct-action day turned in to great Calcutta killings and impact was felt on Frontiers as well. The 4 days Nehru's visit of the tribal areas in 1946 was intruded with large hostile demonstration by Muslim league and its supports. In Waziristan the slogan was shouted against the Congress Party. The Afridis were sitting on the roadside when Nehru visited Khyber and waved shoes, threw stones at Nehru's convoy which broke the glass screen used by Nehru. All these disturbing incidents were reported by the international and Indian Press. The violence was not stopped by the governor and his officers took no steps to avoid the hostile demonstration.[24]

Actually, with Caroe's tacit approval well known religious Leaders were weaved into British network in Pakhtun area around Peshawar like fairy and young pir of Manki sharif and was used to rouse the tribes. He organised sajdanashins for League's cause through his Anjuman- I- Asfia. His large murids posed very effective counter to Abdul Gaffar Khan, which turned out a great advantage for League's cause and resulted in communal polarisation and upsurge in their stand for Pakistan. Caroe gave the impression that the tribes were very much on the side of the League.[25]

They mounted a vicious campaign to paint the two Khan brothers as betrayers of their faith thereby pointing towards the blasphemous act of both the brothers who allowed their children to marry outside the community. However, both the Khan brothers remained blind and obdurate towards the developing situation that demanded insight and imagination to deal with. The irony was that they were dubbed as Hindu agent.[26]

Further strained relationship with the Premier Dr. Khan and difficulty to get along with Caroe, developed complications in the region. His plea was that the party in power had forfeited its popular mandate. This was a clear reflection of favouring the league and sabotaging the Congress Ministry. In February -March 1947 Caroe's unsolicited advice to Khan to tide over the deteriorating the law-and-order situation in the province, he must get rid of the Congress and its Hindu ministers and induct members of Muslim league in to the council of ministers was totally rejected. Hence, unable to bring Khan around, the Governor swung to the other extreme of recommending the dismissal of his ministry followed by Governor's rule and holding of fresh elections.[27]

The Congress alleged him as pro Leaguer and Jinnah and his cohorts did not trust him either. On the hindside Jinnah's paper made no secret as what he viewed of Caroe's subversive role in providing an alternate proposal of independent Pakhtun state to Abdul Gaffar Khan and the Congress ministry in NWFP. The propaganda of Pathanistan alternative to Pakistan was another threat to the ideological foundation of the Pakistan. [28]

Under the 3rd June plan the right of the frontier people to make their own choice was conceded and even imposition of referendum was the doing of Sir Olaf Caroe as he deliberately misled all the staff both in Peshawar and New Delhi. Nehru's agreement to referendum led the Khan brothers fell back on a fanciful for some sort of Pathan independence as a reason for boycotting the referendum.

The proposal of referendum led to the political isolation and virtual liquidation of Khudai khitmatgar among the Pathans and the demand of Paknuistan by Badshah Khan came in haste and vaguely defined. Jinnah denounced the new demand frivolous and spurious just to mislead the people. However, the boycott of referendum decision was an admission of political bankruptcy. [29]

Conclusion

Tribune on the eve of announcement of Caroe's long awaited resignation wrote that history of NWFP would have been differently written if Sir Olaf had not been at the helm of affairs. Surely Caroe had played his part in bringing the realisation of Pakistan. Mountbatten's part in this entire saga is best peripheral. NWFP referendum went in favour of Pakistan. Viceroy Mountbatten's role in detaching the NWFP from the Congress Party control shows that he was fully cooperating to promote British post war defence strategy in the region. As India's Partition was the strategic necessity of Britain and there was hardly any choice [30]

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